

The value of VSD training in the context of product and technology change: Voices from Ethiopian manufacturing industries

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Ethiopia #2 (2024)

At a glance:

This policy brief examines the role of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Ethiopia through an inclusive growth and transformation lens, and identifies lessons learned. The policy brief discusses the impact of technological change and product advancement on employee skills requirements across three industrial sectors in Ethiopia. It explains the main internal and external drivers of product diversification, quality improvement, technological adoption, and work/management reorganization, all of which have had an impact on skills requirements for companies. It asks whether companies believe that vocational skills development (VSD) training programs offered by technical and vocational education and training (TVET) providers meet these skills requirements, and finds that they do in fact believe TVET graduates perform better and adapt more quickly to technological upgrades than school graduates. However, there are still some skills gaps, which means that TVET providers and companies should cooperate more closely to develop training programs that better suit industry requirements.

Background:

Several evaluations have shown that holistic and well-designed TVET programs have the potential to significantly improve the livelihoods and employment opportunities of people. Associated benefits include not only employment and income but also improvements to self-esteem and standing in local communities, reduced aggressive behavior and localized violence, larger positive contributions to local society post-enrolment and positive changes in gender relations (Pompa, 2014).

Vocational Skills Development (VSD) programs are believed to play an important role in contributing to countries' social, economic, and political development. TVET providers offering these VSD programs play a vital role in filling the skills gap and increasing employment opportunities (Lemecha, 2017). In recent decades, the Ethiopian government has pursued ambitious reform of TVET providers, to improve their accessibility, equity, efficiency, and quality, for the growth and transformation of the country.

As part of these reform efforts, the Ethiopian government supported a qualitative in-depth analysis of selected manufacturing industries, to assess how they perceive the skills training programs of TVET providers. It asked 18 manufacturing companies (7 from the textile and garment industry, 5 from the leather industry, and 6 from the metals industry; 50% of them had grown and 50% had shrunk in the

last five years ¹⁾ the following question: Do TVET training programs equip employees with the necessary skills to deal with changes in product design, machinery, work organization and management strategies that have taken place in the last 5 years? This policy brief presents the findings of this qualitative study.

Key findings:

1.1 Diversification and quality improvement changes skill requirements

Companies reported that they were trying to diversify their products to satisfy customer demand and achieve transformation and inclusive growth. In addition to introducing new models of existing products, companies tried to open new product lines, including leather hand bags in the leather industry, t-shirts and military clothes in the textile and garment industries, and various types of tubes, corrugated tin and dangerous fence products in the metal industry. Product diversification and quality improvement were driven by external and internal factors. External drivers included global markets and overall manufacturing costs; internal drivers included the need to minimize wastage of products, reduce production costs, improve delivery times, enhance quality and improve internal satisfaction of the employees. Meanwhile, due to the war, these suppliers (TVET) and demands (industries) are destroyed partially or fully in Tigray. Furthermore, skilled human power is not available anymore in Tigray.

Operators and technicians were more impacted than other occupation levels when new products were introduced, as their skills had to be continually upgraded. These changes led to salary disputes. Companies also faced the difficult challenges of acquiring hard currency and weathering political instability, which hinder technology and product upgrading. Several companies, including Almeda

¹ The selection of companies was based on findings from a previous quantitative survey of 165 companies, under the auspices of the “Skills for industry” project, which evaluates the contribution of vocational skills development to inclusive industrial growth and transformation in developing countries.

Textile, Industrial Parks, and others, were reportedly affected by the war. Several foreign investors were also demanding compensations, loan rescheduling, and insurance coverage. Some of the companies have been damaged, others looted, while some are still intact (CIPE, 2022).

However, all three sectors have introduced new machinery and technology. Government support has been pivotal in this regard—through the removal of taxes on the importation of technologies and provision of aid in the form of loans, work premises and other incentives to drive change. The leather industry has gone furthest in embracing new technology. New machinery can produce a greater variety of higher quality products, making manual work obsolete. The latest machines for cutting, stitching, and lasting only require operators; no other human labor is required to perform these tasks.

1.2 Manufacturing companies value TVET qualifications more than school qualifications for mid- and high-level positions

The survey asked manufacturing companies how they perceive the training provided at TVET institutes. A majority of companies stated that graduates of TVET institutes understand the work situation and work culture better, can do more complex activities, and adapt to industrial transformation more quickly than employees who only have previous work experience and/or school education. Figures 1 and 2 indicate the same.

Figure 1

It is more important that a prospective employee at the highly-skilled level has a TVET qualification rather than only a school education

Figure 2

Figures 3 and 4 show that a majority of the companies agreed that having a large number of mid-level and higher-level employees with TVET qualifications makes it easier to introduce new products into the company.

Having a large number of mid-level employees with TVET qualifications makes it easier to introduce new products in the company

Figure 3

Having a large number of higher-level employees with TVET qualifications makes it easier to introduce new products in the company

Figure 4

Mid-level employees with TVET qualifications adapt faster to new technology (in comparison to those who have no formal skills training)

Figure 5

TVET-qualified employees have played a key role in the introduction of new technologies and machinery, compared to those without formal skills training. This is illustrated in Figures 5 and 6: a majority of companies agreed that mid- and higher-level employees with TVET qualifications adapt faster to new technologies. Similarly, mid- and higher-level employees with TVET qualifications adapt faster to the streamlining of work organization and management across sectors.

Higher-level employees with TVET qualifications adapt faster to new technology (in comparison to those who have no formal skills training)

Figure 6

1.3 TVET training falls short of requirements, so companies also need to train employees in-house

It is also evident that TVET training falls short of requirements, so companies need to train employees in-house. In addition to technical skills, the attitudes

and managerial skills of employees are important. Figures 7 and 8 below show that mid- and higher-level employees engage in diverse and complex tasks. 11 (78.6%) interviewed employers agreed that TVET graduates need less supervision than non-formally trained employees. TVET graduates can also better reduce wastage and defects compared to those who have other qualifications but no formal VSD training.

by providing intensive in-employment training, especially for operators and technicians. The government helps companies in this regard.

Summary of key findings:

- The introduction of new and diversified products and technologies has impacted the skills requirements of manufacturing industries, especially for operator and technician roles.
- Compared to non-formally trained employees, TVET graduates adapt more quickly to these technological changes, product changes, and changes in work organization. They also perform diversified and complex tasks better, and need less supervision. In particular, senior operators with TVET qualifications tend to be better at performing diversified tasks, understanding, and contextualizing new changes, and reducing wastage and defects.
- But TVET training programs do not completely fill the skills gap. Companies also carry out intensive on-the-job training. Stakeholders and the Government support such training to boost productivity.

TVET Graduates versus non-formally trained employees in high-skill positions i.e. Supervision Skills

Figure 7

TVET Graduates versus non-formally trained employees in mid-skill positions i.e. Operator and Technician

Figure 8

However, TVET graduates lack some of the additional skills required to introduce new products and technologies in the leather and shoes industries (less so in the metal industries) whilst maintaining delivery times and staying competitive in local and global markets. Companies therefore fill this gap

Policy recommendation:

Skills development is key to the growth and transformation of manufacturing industries. TVET is vital in this regard, so policymakers must develop TVET policy in-line with industrial policy, making sure that TVET programs are tailored to better meet industry needs.

References:

- CIPE. (2022). The Impact of the War in Northern Ethiopia on Micro, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) and Marginal Economic Actors (MEAs).

- Lemecha, G. (2017). Technical Vocational Education Training Institute Curriculum Development in Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Vocational Research*, 8(3), 16-28.
- Pompa, C. (2014). Economic and Private Sector Professional Evidence and Applied Knowledge Services Helpdesk Request TVET and Skills Training in Fragile and Conflict Affected Countries.

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